

Percent Alteration Accurately Reflects Progression, Intervention And Any Abrupt Changes Occurring In A Population: Plausible Significance Of The Sudden Spurt In Spread of Covid-19

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Abstract

COVID-19 (SARS-Cov-2) is a global pandemic. In this article we have studied the changes taking place in the spread of COVID-19 in a population following interventions. From the plotted percentage graph it was evident that there was control in the growth curve following prolonged intervention from 23 March, 2020 until 31 March 2020. However, a sudden 'spurt' in COVID-19 cases on 1st April 2020 onwards was noted in the percentage graph. Such 'spurt' in COVID-19 cases appeared as a spike in the percentage graph. Following the first peak, two smaller peaks were noted in the graph until 6th April 2020. After 6th April, 2020, growth curve stabilised at around 10% and that was maintained until the end 14th April, 2020. While studying the effect of the sudden spurt on the growth curve by correlation coefficient, we observed that there was a non-significant weak positive correlation between the two variables, that is, COVID-19 cases prior to and after 31 March, 2020 respectively ($p \leq 0.05$). The significance of these results has been discussed in this paper. Overall, the percentage graph reflected that there is a flattening of growth curve post Lockdown at around 10% & the results also confirmed that there was no sign of 'community spread' of the disease among the population, during this period.

Keywords: COVID-19; SARS-Cov-2

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Introduction

The novel coronavirus (SARS- CoV2) originated in Wuhan in Hubei province of China during December 2019; which has now spread across the world; the most affected being the USA and some European countries. Until date there is no new vaccine or therapeutic agents developed against this highly infectious virus that could stop spread of COVID-19 which is known to spread through human to human contact. Under such circumstances, the fight against the disease is focussed on prevention by breaking the chain of SARS-CoV-2. Coronaviruses are a large family of viruses, including those that cause "the common cold" in healthy humans. These viruses account for up to 30 percent of upper respiratory tract infections in adults. This outbreak of COVID-19 marks the third time in recent years and has emerged to cause severe disease and death in human population worldwide. The new coronavirus is closely related to SARS, and its characteristic feature is long latency period before the typical flu-like fever, cough, and shortness of breath manifest. The people infected with this virus may not show any symptoms for up to two weeks, allowing them to pass it on to others in the meantime. As a result, the novel Coronavirus was able to easily spread all over the world.

Due to alarming nature of this disaster world-wide and to

contain further spread of the virus in Indian population, The Authorities declared one day of 'Janata Curfew' on 22 March 2020, from 7AM to 9 PM bringing the country to a standstill. Due to unnerving situation all over India and in different states in Union of India, which showed diverse rate of COVID-19 positive cases, a complete 'National Lockdown' was implemented for 21 days starting from 23rd March, 2020 midnight to Midnight of 14 April, 2020.

In this article, we assessed the nature of spread of COVID-19 before and after intervention using a percentage graph as discussed earlier [1]. It was observed that after curfew/lockdown was implemented on 23rd March, 2020, the percentage change in COVID-19 positive cases maintained a flattened nature until 31st March, 2020. Following which a surge in the number of COVID-19 positive cases among Indian population was recorded in the graph. A major reason for this outbreak was traced back to a 'single source' group. The 'single source' refers to big congregation taking place in the city of Delhi, in middle of March 2020, before the Lockdown was enforced. As per report during the congregation 'social distancing' was not properly maintained. The congregation was an international gathering attended by delegates from various places across the world. It is estimated that several thousand may have attended the said congregation. Before WHO declared COVID-19 as a pandemic

on March 11, 2020, local organisers were possibly not aware that a similar congregation was organised by the same group abroad during end of February where spike in cases of COVID-19 was noted & those attendees may have unknowingly carried the virus with them to India; putting an additional burden to the already existing cases. During the congregation and later after the implementation of country wide Lockdown, many individuals who attended the congregation remained in the place of congregation and later some of the attendees left for their native places across India. During end of March, 2020, many of them were diagnosed to be positive for SARS-COV-2. It now appears individuals from ‘single source’ group may have substantially contributed towards the total number of COVID-19 positive cases across India during that period and later. Various places where the congregation took place in Delhi were designated as ‘Hot Spot’ & such clusters were sealed to prevent further spread of the virus among general population. In this paper we have also studied the effect of the ‘spurt’ on the overall effect of intervention on the spread of COVID-19 in the population.

Method and Results

The present study was carried out on the data collected from the entire Indian population who were diagnosed as COVID-19 positive cases, starting from March 03, 2020 until 09 April, from the websites of Government of India and other national News agencies as described earlier [2].

The Figure 1 reflects the total number of positive cases of COVID-19/day until 09 April, 2020. The number was collected at 10 PM each day from National news agencies & other sources. The graph reflected that there was a linear increase in the number of COVID-19 cases and on 31 March, 2020, there were 1397 cases in the entire country. However, on the next day, 01 April, 2020 there was an abrupt rise of 437 cases and the total number of COVID-19 stood at 1834; showing an increase of 23.8% compared to the previous day. There was an increase of ~500 cases on subsequent days until 09 April, 2020.

THE NUMBER OF COVID-19 CASES FROM 23 MARCH 2020 TO 09 APRIL, 2020.

Figure 1: The graph shows the number of COVID-19 positive individuals in Indian Population at different time points. As evident from the graph, there is an increase in number of positive cases starting from 23 March, 2020 until 09 April, 2020. On 23 March April 2020, there were only 1397 cases and on 9th April the number increased to 5928 cases. That is an increase in 76% of positive cases.

However, from the numbers, it is difficult to ascertain the actual effect of this increase in COVID-19 cases on the stable long term

growth curve that was in place after Lockdown was introduced to control the spread of the virus. The percentage graph depicted in Figure 2 reflects that there was a significant decrease of COVID-19 cases following lockdown and that was stably maintained until 31 March 2020. However, on 1st April, 2020 the percent graph reflected that there was 2.5 folds increase in individuals with COVID-19. This was visible as a ‘small peak’ (P1) in the graph. On subsequent days the percent of positive COVID-19 cases was twofold on 04 April, 2020 and on 06 April it came down to ~1.5 fold and there after the rate of increase in COVID-19 cases stabilized until 9 April, 2020. The trend line clearly indicated a ‘downward slope’ with R² value at 0.193.

PERCENT CHANGE OF COVID-19 CASES FOLLOWING LOCKDOWN

Figure 2: The graph shows the percent change in COVID-19 cases from 23 March, 2020 until 09 April, 2020. The graph reflects that the positive effect of ‘Lockdown’ was maintained from 24 March, 2020 until 31 March, 2020. And on 1st April, 2020, there was an abrupt increase in percentage of cases, particularly due to the addition of positive cases from a ‘single Source’. This trend continued until 06 April 2020 and then subsided to around 10%. However, a downward trend was maintained in the graph.

The percentage of COVID-19 cases from the ‘single source’ group that contributed towards total number of COVID-19 cases in India during 24 hours between 08 April to 09 April, 2020 is shown in Figure 3. The graph reflects that there was contribution of ~30% from ‘single source’ compared to the total number of COVID-19 cases in India. A breakdown of results in different States were: Haryana the contribution from ‘single source’ was 86/134, in Delhi it was 93/93, in UP it was 187/343, in Assam it was 27/28, in Rajasthan it was 48/328, in Kashmir it was 9/9 & in Tamil Nadu it was 42/48 respectively.

PERCENT INCREASE OF COVID-19 CASES IN 24 HOURS FROM ONE SOURCE IN DIFFERENT STATES OF INDIA

Figure 3: The graph shows the contribution of COVID-19 cases from the ‘Single Source’ as compared to total cases reported in different states in union of India, during 24 hours.

The Figure 4A & 4B reflects highlights the pattern of the ‘spurt’ from 1st April, 2020 to 9th April, 2020. The Figure-4A shows the number of COVID-19 in the above mentioned period which appears as a linear graph. However, Figure-4B representing percentage of change during the same period as mentioned above clearly indicates the presence of three different peaks from 1st April, 2020 to 6th April, 2020; the subtle changes was not apparent in Figure:4A. The Figure 4B reflects that there are three small peaks appearing on 1st April, 2020 (P1), 4th April, 2020 (P2) & 6th April, 2020 (P3) respectively. It also indicated that the percentage of cases after 6th April 2020 onwards regressed and by 9th April, 2020, the percent of COVID-19 cases had stabilized. The Figure: 4B also reflected that due to the spurt the R² value was low at 0.171.

SUDDEN SPURT IN COVID-19 CASES AFTER 31 MARCH, 2020 DURING LOCKDOWN

Figure 4A & 4B: The Figure- 4A shows the number of COVID-19 cases from 01 April, 2020 TO 09 April, 2020 when abrupt increase in COVID-19 cases was noted. The figure-4B shows the percentage change in COVID-19 cases during the same period. In the graph the spurt is clearly visible as three small peaks were made, designated as P1, P2 & P3 respectively. However the trend line shows a downward slope implying the spurt did not immediately disturb the downward trend in COVID-19 cases.

A correlation coefficient graph as shown in Figure 5, representing the two variables, that is percentage of Covid-19 cases prior to and following the ‘spurt’, showed a weak positive correlation and the p value was at a non-significant level (≤ 0.05).

CORRELATION BETWEEN PERCENT CHANGES IN COVID-19 CASES BEFORE AND AFTER 31 MARCH, 2020

Figure 5: A correlation coefficient graph reflects that there is weak correlation between percentage of COVID-19 cases prior to after 31 March, 2020. The p value at 0.440872 is non-significant ($p \leq 0.05$).

This probably suggested that ‘spurt’ in Covid-19 cases did not

have any immediate impact on the underlying trend of the growth curve.

Discussion

The recent disaster caused all over the world by the advent of the corona virus has prompted a massive global efforts to contain and slow the spread of this virus in addition to finding a cure/vaccine for COVID-19. However, regardless of those efforts over the last few months, it has not been possible to contain the virus without appropriate and timely intervention as it mostly tends to spread from person-to-person through respiratory droplets produced when an infected person coughs or sneezes. The dangerous part of SARS-CoV-2 infection is its ability to spread within a community if not stopped at the right time; the community spread being in an exponential manner at a later stage. The enormity of the disaster is starkly visible in the USA, Italy, Spain & Germany; none of these countries had introduced any stringent restrictions on the movement of people across the country when the number of COVID-19 cases was small. India however, was an exception as it introduced various stringent measures restricting movement of people at an early stage, when the number of COVID-19 positive cases was small. Until 31 March, 2020, the measures taken were able to slow down the spread of the contagious virus (SARS-COV-2), and rate was more or less stable until 31 March 2020. However, the picture abruptly changed from 1st April 2020 onwards, when there was a substantial increase in COVID-19 positive cases. Due to this abrupt increase in number of positive cases, new stringent actions were initiated by the Authority to identify, isolate and quarantine the COVID-19 individuals and hundreds of ‘hot spots’ were identified in different regions of the country. However, in midst of such discouraging picture, some states maintained a minimal number of COVID-19 cases, suggesting an effective implementation of Lockdown in those states. These states included Tripura, Assam, Manipur etc.; wherein the total number of COVID-19 cases, on an average is below 100 as of 9 April, 2020. Nevertheless, the situation across India has the potential to change abruptly as many new cases are surfacing every day (For instance, in Delhi itself 52 persons were found to be COVID-19 positive within 24 hours).

The silver lining so far, about this highly infectious disease is that there are many instances where individuals with COVID-19 have recovered completely world-wide including India. Many such recovered patients showed presence of antibodies against the coronavirus, SARS-cov-2, and transfer of ‘Plasma’ taken from such recovered patients were able to cure patients suffering from COVID-19. Studies from South Korea also have confirmed the role of immunity in recovery of patients. In a study in the USA, it was demonstrated that specific T cells could have played a role in fighting the disease at late stage of infection with SARS-COV-2. Therefore, it was speculated that an earlier induction of specific T cell response against the SARS-CoV-2 may become a game changer for the treatment of COVID-19. Some earlier studies have demonstrated that *in vivo* induction of

inflammatory FLT-3L could generate a T cell response *in vivo* [3]. In one of our earlier studies, we were able to generate a long-term protective immune response against malignant pulmonary cells by Flt3L therapy following irradiation *in situ* [4, 5]. All such studies have repeatedly demonstrated that a long term memory T-cell mediated response is vital for eradicating a viral infection. Towards that perception, a recent article being published in the journal Cell has demonstrated that a blood samples collected from a group of 20 people who were exposed to SARS but were never exposed to the novel coronavirus, had cross-reactive T cells that were capable of recognizing & responding faster to the novel coronavirus as illustrated in Figure 6 [6].

UNEXPOSED INDIVIDUALS RESPOND TO CORONAVIRUS SARS-CoV-2

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Figure 6: The figure has been taken from the recent issue of Cell Journal which shows that immunocyte collected from individuals who were unexposed to SARS-CoV-2 responded to the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2. It is suggested that those individuals had prior immunization to SARS-2 and cross reacted to SARS-CoV-2.

However, in the present scenario the only way to stop the spread of novel coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2 is by implementing sustained physical intervention. In this article it is demonstrated that the spread of SARS-Cov-2 within the Indian population was contained by implementing total Lockdown with ‘social distancing’ at the appropriate time. It was revealed in this study that (a) Much of the success of Lockdown depended on ‘early detection’ of nature of spread of COVID-19 in the population to facilitate fine tuning of the intervention already in place; (b) Unprecedented changes taking place in the number of COVID-19 cases, due to an unforeseen event was detectable at an early

stage from the plotted percent graph; (c) The comparative study of the rate of change in COVID-19 cases prior to and after Lockdown had no immediate significant; (d) The ‘Spurt’ noted in the graph after 31st March, 2020 had weak positive correlation with the overall increase in COVID-19 cases & (e) The percent graph also elucidated that the long term down trend in the rate of COVID-19 cases remained intact and the population did not show any signs of entering the third phase of community spread of COVID-19 as of April 09, 2020.

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